

Excitonic Refractive Index Change in High Purity GaAs Modulator at Room Temperature for Optical Fiber Communication Network

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Abstract—In this paper, we have compared and analyzed the electroabsorption properties between with and without excitonic effect bulk in high purity GaAs spatial light modulator for optical fiber communication network. The electroabsorption properties such as absorption spectra, change in absorption spectra, change in refractive index and extinction ratio has been calculated. We have also compared the result of absorption spectra and change in absorption spectra with the experimental results and found close agreement with experimental results.

Keywords—Exciton, Refractive index change, Extinction ratio.

I. INTRODUCTION

THERE has been considerable interest in the electric field dependence of optical properties in GaAs material with excitonic effect. The importance of exciton effects was cleared by Dow and Redfield [1] below and far above the bandgap. For the first time, a clear excitonic absorption peak was measured at room temperature in high purity GaAs [2]. The shift of electroabsorption near the band-gap to the lower energy was experimentally verified [3]. The studies of the advantages of exciton effects in the presence of electric field were increased in recent years. It is also important that the size of changes in refractive index due to electroabsorption is attractive for electro-optic devices. In this paper, we have compared electroabsorption properties with and without exciton effect and verified with experimental result. The change in absorption coefficient, change in refractive index and extinction ratio in the presence of electric field have been calculated.

II. THEORETICAL MODELS

The electroabsorption with exciton band and continuum band transition including Gaussian function and Sommerfield factor at RT can be defined [4]

$$\alpha(\hbar\omega) = \frac{4e^2\pi^2\hbar}{nmcd} \{ \alpha_e(x) + \alpha_c(x) \} \quad (1)$$

with $\alpha_e(x) = G(x)$ and $\alpha_c(x) = f\delta(x) + S(x)$

$$x = \frac{\hbar\omega - E_{ex}}{\hbar\Gamma} \quad (2)$$

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$$G(x) = Q_X e^{-x^2/2} \quad (3)$$

$$\delta(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-2\pi x}} \quad (4)$$

$$S(x) = \frac{\pi e^{\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{x}}}}{x \sinh\left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{x}}\right)} \quad (5)$$

$$f = \frac{2|M_{cv}|^2}{\pi m a_0^3 \hbar \omega} \quad (6)$$

where is Planck constant, e is electron charge, n is refractive index, m is free electron mass, c is speed of light in vacuum, d is thickness of active layer, f is oscillator strength, $\delta(x)$ is delta function, $G(x)$ is Gaussian function, Q_X is exciton quenching factor, $S(x)$ is Sommerfield factor, f is oscillator strength, M_{cv} is dipole matrix element, $E_{ex} = E_g + \Delta E$ is excitation energy and a_0 is bohr radius.

The exciton peak shift can be written for low field and high field, respectively as [4]:

$$\Delta E = -6 \times 10^{-3} \frac{9}{8} f^2 \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta E = -19 \times 10^{-3} \frac{9}{8} f^2 \quad (8)$$

where f is reduced electric field which is defined as $f = F/F_i$ where F_i is ionization field and F is electric field.

The half-width at half maximum of exciton $\hbar\Gamma$ can be defined as [4].

$$\hbar\Gamma = 26 \times 6.5 \times 10^{-3} \frac{1}{f} e^{-10/3f} \quad (9)$$

The relationship between change in absorption and refractive index change near the absorption edge for excitonic transitions is given by the Kramers-Kronig dispersion relation [5].

$$\Delta n = \frac{c}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\Delta \alpha dE}{\hbar \omega^2 - E^2} \quad (10)$$

where c is velocity of light, E is transition energy $\hbar\omega$ is photon energy.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

For the simulation, the software based on Mathcad has been used in this work. The absorption coefficient with Coulomb

interaction including exciton and continuum band at room temperature as well as associated with electric field in the presence of both exciton and continuum broadening has been considered in this work.

In Fig. 1, we have compared the structure of electroabsorption modulators which are waveguide type and surface-normal type. The waveguide has many disadvantages such as difficult to fabricate a 2D array, poor misalignment tolerance, and large size and fabrication complication whereas surface-normal type has also disadvantage such as short optical path length.

Fig. 1 Structure of electroabsorption modulator

Fig. 2 Electric field distribution in high purity and low purity GaAs at two different voltages

The electric field distribution between high purity and low purity GaAs has been compared. Fig. 2 shows that the electric field at high purity GaAs has distributed widely than that of low purity GaAs.

Fig. 3 shows the absorption spectra with excitonic effects for high purity GaAs with $5\mu\text{m}$ thickness with impurity concentration of 10^{14} cm^{-3} at various electric fields. The linewidth broadening of exciton and stark energy shift with excitonic effect due to external applied voltage have been included in our calculation based on (8), (9), and (10) respectively. The linewidth broadening due to continuum

band absorption is also included. In Fig. 3, the absorption spectra after exciton peak in experimental result at lower energy shows higher value than that of our result because this may be due to the reflection loss, coupling loss and substrate loss. The excitonic peak remains stable toward the lower energy having large red shift even at electric field of 70 kV/cm indicating that the electric field is uniform inside the active layer, which implies very high purity in active region. In the Fig. 3, the calculated absorption spectra without exciton effect at two different electric field is also shown.

Fig. 3 Absorption spectra of theoretical and experimental at two different electric field

Fig. 4 Electroabsorption change of measured and theoretical results with and without exciton

Our numerical simulation discussed for GaAs bulk material with the thickness and carrier concentration of $5\mu\text{m}$ of $1 \times 10^{14}\text{ cm}^{-3}$, respectively as shown in Table I. The material dependence parameters such as reduced mass of electron and hole (μ) and bandgap E_g is taken as $0.069 m_0$ and 1.425 eV respectively. The change in absorption coefficient as a function of photon energy with and without exciton absorption at the

electric field of 70 kV/cm as well as measured absorption coefficient with exciton at the same electric field in shown Fig. 4. It is shown that the calculated change in absorption coefficient has closed agreement with the experimental ones. Our calculation shows that the change in absorption coefficient with exciton and without exciton was compared at photon energy of 1.406 eV. It is found that the change in absorption coefficient is 2.19 times higher with exciton effect than that of without exciton effect.

Fig. 5 Change in absorption spectra as a function of photon energy (in narrow range of photon energy)

Fig. 5 shows the change in absorption spectra as a function of photon energy in the required lasing wavelength of the device. The change in absorption spectra with exciton effect in this range is nearly coincide with the experimental result. In this range, the change in absorption spectra is about 2.19 times higher with exciton than that of without exciton effect.

The basic method of our simulation is used for the calculation of refractive index change by using Kramers-Kronig dispersion relation. The change in refractive index has been calculated from the absorption coefficient change association with the applied electric field of 70 kV/cm below the bandgap as shown in Fig. 6. The refractive index change with exciton absorption is estimated to be about 2.08 times higher than that of without exciton effect at photon energy of 1.406eV.

Fig. 7 shows the extinction ratio as a function of photon energy with and without exciton effect. The extinction ratio with and without exciton effect has been calculated based on the relation $10\log(e^{-\Delta\alpha d})$, where, $\Delta\alpha$ is the change in absorption coefficient and d is the thickness of active layer. The extinction ratio is same upto photon energy of 1.38 eV and the gap between the extinction ratio with and without exciton effect is increased up to 1.41 eV. The extinction ratio is higher with exciton effect than without exciton effect in the range of 1.38 eV to 1.41 eV and it is 2.06 times higher at photon energy of 1.406 eV. At this photon energy, the extinction ratio is estimated to be 13dB at 70 kV/cm.

Fig. 6 Calculated refractive index change with and without exciton

Fig. 7 Calculated extinction ratio with and without exciton effect

TABLE I
PARAMETERS USED IN THE CALCULATION

Parameters	Value	Units
active layer thickness (d)	5	μm
carrier concentration (N)	1×10^{14}	cm^{-3}
ionization field (F_i)	69	kV/cm
detuning energy (ΔE)	25	meV
bandgap (E_g)	1.429	eV

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have calculated the change in absorption coefficient, change in refractive index and extinction ratio associated with exciton effect at two different electric fields. We obtained the good agreement with experimental results. We have concluded that the performance characteristics such as refractive index change, extinction ratio of bulk high purity GaAs layer for spatial light modulator can be enhanced with exciton effect. It is found that the change in absorption coefficient is almost double with exciton effect which consequently doubles the change in refractive index in exciton effect than in without exciton. The refractive change in this work is reached nearly to the refractive change of quantum

well structured external modulator. The extinction ratio has been estimated to be about 2.06times higher with exciton effect than without.

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